

An Analysis of Machine Learning and Deep Learning Research in Aviation Using Scientific Measurements

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>RESEARCH ARTICLE</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords: Aviation Machine Learning Deep Learning Management Information Systems</p> <hr/> <p>Received: 03 October 2025 Revised: 12 December 2025 Accepted: 22 December 2025</p>	<p>This study examines the scientific development of machine learning and deep learning in the aviation sector using scientific measurement analysis methods. Aviation is a highly regulated field, in which safety is paramount and large amounts of data are generated; machine learning and deep learning-based solutions are utilized in numerous sub-fields such as predictive maintenance, air traffic management, flight safety and risk analysis, management information systems, and aircraft design. However, most of the existing literature consists of review articles focused on specific application areas rather than analyzing the intellectual structure, collaboration networks, and development dynamics of the field at a macro level. To address this gap, the study evaluated publications obtained from the Web of Science database using the keywords '(machine learning OR deep learning) AND aviation' using CiteSpace software. The analyses involved citation clustering, topic categories, and citation burst methods and provided a detailed examination of the prominent machine learning and deep learning methods in 25 critical publications showing citation bursts. This study provides a comprehensive bibliometric mapping of the field, revealing distinct evolutionary phases, citation bursts, and emerging research fronts in aviation-specific ML/DL applications. The findings reveal the most common methods and themes in aviation, as well as future research directions. The study contributes to the literature by mapping the intellectual structure, identifying critical trends, and providing a guiding framework for researchers.</p>

1. Introduction

The aviation sector, an essential pillar of the global economy and transportation, has often been at the forefront of innovation. Today, with the advent of big data, this industry faces both challenges and opportunities. The efficient utilization of the large volume of data generated by aircraft sensors, air traffic control systems, and maintenance logs is crucial for improving safety, operational efficiency, and predictive maintenance (Puranik et al., 2020; Stanton et al., 2023).

Management information systems (MIS) are a fundamental aspect of the aviation sector, enhancing operational efficiency, supporting strategic decision-making, and facilitating data-driven management processes (Laudon & Laudon, 2020). MIS are now able to make use of big data analytics, cloud computing, and artificial intelligence

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and this enables airlines to remain competitive via dynamic pricing, demand forecasting, customer relationship management, and supply chain optimization (O'Brien & Marakas, 2021). The integration of machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) algorithms into MIS infrastructures enhances the effectiveness of decision support systems, supporting the automation of business processes and the success of digital transformation projects (Turban et al., 2018).

In such a landscape, ML and DL applications are most effective for handling complex data and offer disruptive solutions for the aviation industry (Wei et al., 2022). They address major problems, including anomaly detection, flight path optimization, aircraft component failure prediction, and air traffic flow modeling (Wang et al., 2020). Given this rapid growth, it is important to systematically investigate the intellectual social structure and dynamic evolution of this multidisciplinary field.

The objective of the current study was to conduct a thorough bibliometric analysis of scientific papers in the WoS database with key words: 'machine learning' or 'deep learning' and 'aviation' enabling the identification of the knowledge structure, hotspots, and development trajectory of this intersection. The purpose of this study is to visualize the literature on ML and DL applications in aviation based on empirical studies, apply a quantitative approach, and provide an overview of the research field. Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following research questions:

- 1: What is the intellectual structure and knowledge foundation of ML/DL research in aviation, as revealed through citation clustering and co-citation patterns?
- 2: How has the field evolved over time in terms of research themes, citation bursts, and disciplinary integration with other scientific domains?
- 3: Which ML and DL methodologies are most frequently adopted in aviation applications, and what are the emerging algorithmic trends in this interdisciplinary field?
- 4: What are the landmark publications and research fronts that have shaped the development of ML/DL applications in aviation?

By structuring the investigation in this way, this study makes several notable contributions to both theory and practice.

Theoretically, this research advances scholarly understanding by comprehensively mapping the intellectual structure at the intersection of ML/DL and aviation. Specifically, it reveals the field's knowledge foundation, interdisciplinary links, and theoretical development. The study contributes a macro-level overview by using quantitative citation network analysis to systematically expose knowledge structure and collaboration patterns, in contrast to reviews focused on specific domains (e.g., predictive maintenance, air traffic management). Furthermore, it identifies three developmental phases—exploratory applications (2010-2015), methodological refinement (2016-2019), and integrated intelligent systems (2020-2025)—offering a temporal framework for understanding technology maturation. By analyzing the ML/DL algorithms utilized in landmark publications with citation bursts, this work highlights methodological trends and algorithmic evolution, providing concrete directions for future research within the field.

In practice, the findings provide actionable insights for aviation practitioners and MIS managers. Identifying proven ML/DL applications across safety, operations, and maintenance provides a technology adoption roadmap grounded in empirical evidence from highly cited publications. Citation burst analysis highlights new methodologies and emerging research fronts, signaling future trends and helping organizations anticipate innovations.

For the analysis, we used CiteSpace, a leading tool for scientific knowledge mapping and bibliometric network visualization (Chen, 2006). This study has three main contributions: (i) mapping this interdisciplinary field's intellectual structure; (ii) summarizing key trends, themes, and methodologies; and (iii) suggesting future research directions based on the findings.

2. Theoretical Background

This study's theoretical background lies at the intersection of four fields: Machine Learning (ML), Deep Learning (DL), Aviation, and Bibliometric Analysis. This framework allows a clarification of the research, the variables, and their context within related work.

2.1. Theoretical basis of the study and concepts addressed

2.1.1. Machine learning and deep learning

ML is a subfield of Artificial Intelligence (AI) that enables computer systems to learn from data rather than explicit programming. ML consists of techniques that automate the discovery of patterns and relationships in large datasets (Bishop, 2006).

Deep Learning (DL) is a subset of ML and involves the artificial construction of deep neural networks (multi-layered ANNs) that represent high-order abstractions of data (Goodfellow et al., 2016). DL outperforms classical ML in areas of complex data which are particularly relevant to aviation, such as image recognition, natural language processing, and high-dimensional time series (LeCun et al., 2015).

2.1.2. Aviation sector and application areas

The subject context and dependent variable of this study are the aviation industry. This industry, carefully regulated and prioritizing safety, is also a vibrant field with copious data available. The three predominant applications of ML and DL in aviation are: (1) predictive maintenance, which involves predicting aircraft component failure time with a view to lowering overall maintenance costs and enhancing flight safety (Wang et al., 2020), (2) air traffic management (ATM), which aims to increase airspace capacity, reduce delays and manage collision risks, (3) flightsafety and hazard analysis, which concerns the automation of identification of potential safety hazards from flight operation data (Puranik et al., 2020) and airplane design/optimization (Wei et al., 2022). The last of these includes aerodynamics analysis, structural mechanics simulation etc., which can significantly reduce the computing time for molecule evaluation in design optimization.

2.1.3. Bibliometric analysis and CiteSpace

The methodological principle of this study is a bibliometric method developed within the field of scientific knowledge mapping and network analysis. Bibliometrics is one such technique for the quantitative analysis of the dynamics and structure in scientific fields, which allows for the study of relationships existing between publications, citations, and authors (Pritchard, 1969). CiteSpace, one of the most widely used bibliometric tools, was designed to discern and illustrate emerging trends and passing patterns in scientific literature (Chen, 2006). The CiteSpace software was used in the present study for citation clustering and burst analysis. Furthermore, citation clustering has the capacity to identify major intellectual clusters (topics) and subtopics in a research field by grouping papers cited together, while burst analysis of citations can delineate classic papers which have a sudden increase in citations within specific periods, as well as emerging trends. One of the main contributions of the study is its focus on machine learning and deep learning techniques used by certain of the publications under analysis.

2.2. Summary of the current literature

While most research on aviation applications provides a broad overview, only a few studies—primarily comprehensive review papers—focus on specific subtopics such as DL-based technologies for predictive maintenance. These reviews indicate, on a technical basis, the models that solve particular problems (Wang et al., 2020; Wei et al., 2022). However, very few of these studies have focused on the macro intellectual structure and developmental dynamics of the field (author, institution, country collaboration, citation patterns).

Published bibliometric works tend to cover broader subjects, such as AI or Big Data, and often report on areas other than aviation-related ones. This gap will be addressed by the present study, which examines the scientific development of ML and DL specifically in aviation, and analyzes WoS data using citation bursts, clustering, and subject categories in CiteSpace. The advantages of this approach are particularly evident in the key publications, where citation bursts are analyzed in greater detail, thereby strengthening the scientific contribution.

3. Methodology

This research was conducted to quantitatively analyze the intellectual structure and development dynamics of the scientific literature at the intersection of ML/DL and Aviation. The method used in the study is based on Bibliometric Analysis, which enables the systematic examination of large scientific data sets.

3.1. Research model

The use of the bibliometric analysis model in this study enables the observation of a scientific field's structure and development through citation relationships among publications and between co-authors. In this case, the bibliometric approach appears as a tool for mapping patterns and trends in scientific production, notably by applying science-mapping tools (Chen, 2006). Compared with a standard systematic review, this approach has the advantage of allowing objective, quantitative assessment of the literature at the macro level.

3.2. Data set and preprocessing

The systematic search was conducted in the Web of Science (WoS) Core Collection database to identify relevant publications at the intersection of machine learning/deep learning and aviation. The search query was executed using the following keyword string: TS=("machine learning" OR "deep learning") AND aviation), where "TS" represents Topic Search covering titles, abstracts, keywords, and Keywords Plus fields.

The timeframe was set from 2010 to 2025, allowing the search to capture the rapid development period of ML/DL applications in the aviation sector. This temporal scope was chosen to reflect the emergence and maturation of deep learning technologies following the breakthrough of AlexNet in 2012 (Krizhevsky et al., 2012) and the subsequent adoption of these technologies in aviation domains.

The initial search yielded 1,374 records. To ensure comprehensive coverage, all document types indexed in WoS were included in the analysis: articles, conference papers, review articles, proceedings papers, and book chapters. Only English-language publications were included due to the language's dominance in international scientific communication, and to maintain consistency during the bibliometric analysis. The complete dataset was exported in the "Full Record and Cited References" format (.txt) to enable comprehensive citation network analysis in CiteSpace.

It was decided not to apply additional manual filtering or exclusion criteria in order to preserve the objectivity of the bibliometric approach, and capture the full intellectual landscape of ML/DL research in aviation, as represented in the WoS database.

3.3. Measurement tools and analysis methods

CiteSpace software (version 6.2.R4), widely used for the visualization and analysis of scientific knowledge fields, served as the primary measurement and analysis tool for this research. CiteSpace can create scientific knowledge maps and identify the main clusters, key nodes, and landmark publications within the intellectual structure (Chen, 2006).

CiteSpace Configuration Parameters: To ensure methodological transparency and reproducibility, the following parameter settings were applied throughout the analysis:

1. Time Slicing: Annual slices from 2010 to 2025 (1 year per slice)
2. Selection Criteria: Top 50 most-cited or most-frequent items per time slice using g-index (k=25)
3. Pruning: Pathfinder network scaling and Minimum Spanning Tree (MST) algorithms
4. Threshold Settings: Default values (c=2, cc=2, ccv=20), where c represents citation threshold, cc represents co-citation threshold, and ccv represents co-citation coefficient variance
5. Link Strength: Cosine similarity coefficient for measuring the relationship strength between nodes

The dataset downloaded from WoS was subjected to three basic types of bibliometric analysis:

Citation Clustering: The citation relationships between studies were used to identify closely related scientific topics (intellectual clusters) in the field. These clusters reveal the field's fundamental research topics and focal points.

Subject Category Analysis: By examining the publications' WoS categories, the analysis determined the scientific disciplines with which ML/DL-Aviation research intersects with most frequently, and the changes in this intersection over time.

Citation Burst Analysis: Arguably the most important analysis in the study, it identified articles that experienced a sudden large increase in citations within a known publication time frame (citation burst). These outlets are responsible for innovative, radical, and groundbreaking ideas in the discipline. Special attention was given to the top 25 publications with burst citations and to these publications' specific ML/DL methods. In this review, we

conducted a qualitative content analysis using quantitative data to investigate methodological trends and the best-performing algorithms in the field.

4. Findings

The citation network for papers published in 2015 – 2025 is depicted in Fig. The evolution of co-occurring theme clusters in the literature is illustrated in Figure 2. The horizontal axis is the timeline, and each row is a cluster. Each color region contains a cluster of thematically-related publications. The size of nodes reflects the number of citations for each study, and color gradations indicate date of publication. The modularity value ($Q = 0.8413$) and the average Silhouette value ($S = 0.9546$) indicate that these clusters are very consistent in content.

The literature network of 1,372 publications from 2015 to 2025 was analyzed using CiteSpace, yielding 16 significant clusters. The modularity coefficient $Q = 0.8413$ and the average Silhouette value $S = 0.9546$ were computed for the networks. These numbers indicate that the clusters are both clearly distinguished and compact.

Fig. 1: Citation Clustering Map of the Literature on Machine Learning and Deep Learning in Aviation (Created by the authors).

An examination of the distribution of clusters by theme reveals that the literature is divided between technical and applied focuses. The largest clusters are labeled #0 “Commercial Aviation,” #1 “Flight Delay Prediction,” #2 “Systematic Review,” #3 “Automatic Threat Recognition,” and #4 “Future Research Trajectory,” respectively.

Fig. 2: Timeline of Citation Clusters in the Literature on Machines and Deep Learning in Aviation (Created by the authors).

Cluster #0 (Commercial Aviation): Includes work focused on general aviation operations, fleet management, and data-driven decision support systems.

Cluster #1 (Flight Delay Prediction): Focuses on machine learning models (particularly XGBoost, RF, CNN) for predicting flight delays. Cluster #2 (Systematic Review): Covers review studies synthesizing the applications of machine learning and deep learning in aviation. Cluster #3 (Automatic Threat Recognition): Includes deep learning-based approaches, particularly in security screening, image processing, and object recognition. Cluster #4 (Future Research Trajectory): Represents studies that bibliometrically analyze trends in the literature and future research directions. Among the smaller clusters, themes #5 “Using Wavelet-Based Nonlinear Feature,” #9 “Feasibility Test,” #10 “Big Data,” #12 “Passive Brain–Computer Interface Application,” and #14 “Remaining Useful Life Prediction” stand out. These clusters reflect application-oriented subfields such as predictive maintenance, human–machine interaction, data-intensive analysis, and remaining useful life (RUL) estimation.

The average publication years of the clusters (2018–2022 range) indicate that these themes coincide with the rise of deep learning-based modeling and predictive analytics. The findings reveal, post-2020, the aviation sector’s clear concentration on flight safety, delay prediction, autonomous systems, and data-intensive analytics.

Figure 3 shows the co-occurrence network constructed using WoS subject categories. Each colored cluster represents thematically related disciplinary fields in the literature. The size of the nodes indicates the number of publications in each category, while the connecting lines represent collaborations between categories and interdisciplinary interactions. The network’s modularity value ($Q = 0.4142$) and average Silhouette value ($S = 0.819$) indicate that the clusters are meaningfully distinct, yet interdisciplinary interactions are also high. Figure 3 shows the distribution of studies across aviation, machinery, and deep learning. In the network structure, six main clusters stand out. The largest, Engineering, Mechanical, at the center of the literature, reflects the field’s technical and engineering-based structure. This cluster establishes strong connections with Computer Science, Information Systems, Transportation Science & Technology, and Remote Sensing, demonstrating the intensity of interdisciplinary interaction. The Engineering, Industrial cluster focuses on production, automation, and system optimization, while the Public, Environmental & Occupational Health cluster represents studies related to human factors and environmental impacts. Overall, the network reveals that machine and deep learning research in aviation has a multidisciplinary structure that brings together engineering, information technology, transportation, and environmental fields.

Fig. 3: Network of Subject Categories for Machine and Deep Learning Studies in Aviation (Created by the authors).

The citation burst table created in Figure 4 shows the studies that experienced sudden increases in citations (citation bursts) between 2015 and 2025 and specific periods of these bursts. The related analysis enables identifying high-impact articles quickly and shifting the direction of the literature.

Top 25 References with the Strongest Citation Bursts

References	Year	Strength	Begin	End	2015 - 2025
Borghini G, 2014, NEUROSCI BIOBEHAV R, V44, P58, DOI 10.1016/j.neubiorev.2012.10.003, DOI	2014	3.26	2015	2019	
Rusk N, 2016, NAT METHODS, V13, P35, DOI 10.1038/nmeth.3707, DOI	2016	4.34	2017	2021	
Krizhevsky A, 2017, COMMUN ACM, V60, P84, DOI 10.1145/3065386, DOI	2017	6.7	2018	2022	
Goodfellow I, 2016, ADAPT COMPUT MACH LE, V0, P1	2016	5.16	2018	2021	
Ren SQ, 2015, ADV NEUR IN, V28, P0, DOI 10.1109/TPAMI.2016.2577031, DOI	2015	2.74	2018	2020	
Choi S, 2016, IEEEAIAA DIGIT AVION, V0, P0	2016	4.06	2019	2021	
Melynk I, 2016, J AEROSP INFORM SYST, V13, P161, DOI 10.2514/1.1010394, DOI	2016	2.85	2019	2020	
He KM, 2016, PROC CVPR IEEE, V0, PP770, DOI 10.1109/CVPR.2016.90, DOI	2016	5.92	2020	2021	
Puranik TG, 2018, J AEROSP INFORM SYST, V15, P22, DOI 10.2514/1.1010582, DOI	2018	4.11	2020	2021	
Puranik T, 2017, J AIRCRAFT, V54, P2285, DOI 10.2514/1.C034196, DOI	2017	3.93	2020	2021	
Chen TQ, 2016, KDD16: PROCEEDI ERY AND DATA MINING, V0, PP785, DOI	2016	3.44	2020	2021	
Basora L, 2019, AEROSPACE-BASEL, V6, P0, DOI 10.3390/aerospace6110117, DOI	2019	3.21	2020	2022	
Janakiraman VM, 2018, KDD18: P OVERY & DATA MINING, V0, PP406, DOI	2018	3.16	2020	2022	
Puranik TG, 2020, J AEROSP INFORM SYST, V17, P51, DOI 10.2514/1.1010772, DOI	2020	3.16	2020	2022	
Tong C, 2018, APPL SOFT COMPUT, V73, P344, DOI 10.1016/j.asoc.2018.07.061, DOI	2018	2.95	2020	2021	
Sheridan K, 2020, AIAA SCITECH 2020 FORUM, V0, P0	2020	2.95	2020	2021	
Memarzadeh M, 2020, AEROSPACE-BASEL, V7, P0, DOI 10.3390/aerospace7080115, DOI	2020	3.56	2021	2023	
Lee H, 2020, AEROSPACE-BASEL, V7, P0, DOI 10.3390/aerospace7060073, DOI	2020	3.1	2021	2022	
Huang G, 2017, PROC CVPR IEEE, V0, PP2261, DOI 10.1109/CVPR.2017.243, DOI	2017	2.61	2021	2022	
Murça MCR, 2018, TRANSPORT RES C-EMER, V97, P324, DOI 10.1016/j.trc.2018.10.021, DOI	2018	3.33	2022	2023	
Zhang XG, 2019, DECIS SUPPORT SYST, V116, P48, DOI 10.1016/j.dss.2018.10.009, DOI	2019	3.19	2022	2023	
Oehling J, 2019, SAFETY SCI, V114, P89, DOI 10.1016/j.ssci.2018.12.018, DOI	2019	2.91	2022	2023	
Wang L, 2018, SAFETY SCI, V102, P14, DOI 10.1016/j.ssci.2017.09.027, DOI	2018	2.91	2022	2023	
Zhang XG, 2021, SAFETY SCI, V142, P0, DOI 10.1016/j.ssci.2021.105390, DOI	2021	3.36	2023	2025	
Heyne J, 2021, FUEL, V290, P0, DOI 10.1016/j.fuel.2020.120004, DOI	2021	3.02	2023	2025	

Fig. 4: Analysis of the Citation Explosion in Aviation Machinery and Deep Learning Research (Created by the authors).

The “Year” column in Figure 4 shows the year of publication; the “Strength” value indicates the strength of the citation explosion. The ‘Begin’ and ‘End’ columns indicate the length of the explosion in years. The red line on the graph shows the period during which the explosion was effective, and the blue line, period during which the publication received moderate number of citations.

Based on the analysis results, the largest peak occurred in a work by Krizhevsky et al. (2012) (Strength = 6.7; 2018–2022). The CNN architecture was first established in this study and serves as the basis for DL algorithms

and applications in image processing, fault detection, and aviation autonomous systems. This was followed by the Generative Adversarial Networks (GAN) proposed by Goodfellow et al., (2016) (Strength = 5.16; 2018–2021). Rusk (2016) carried an article [Strength = 4.34 (2017–2021)] that was also highlighted in methodology framework, however, more impactful were Puranik et al. (2020) (Strength = 4.11; 2020–2021) and Basora et al., (2019) (Strength = 3.21; 2020–2022), in machine learning-based flight safety, air traffic management and predictive maintenance. Heyne (2021) (Strength = 3.02; 2023–2025) is also noteworthy. These papers reflect the growing prominence of fuel efficiency, energy optimization, and sustainable aviation themes in the discipline. The 2015–2025 decade can be assessed, in broad terms, in three phases. The years 2015–2018 witnessed the development of the basic deep learning architectures (e.g., CNNs, ResNets, and GANs), and the emergence of methodological support. A surge in aviation-specific applications was observed during 2018–2022, primarily in fault detection, flight delay prediction, and predictive maintenance. The 2022–2025 period reflects the research trend toward sustainability, energy efficiency, and minimizing environmental impact. All this suggests the emergence of a more holistic approach that incorporates environmental coupling.

5. Results and Discussion

Through scientific measurement technique (bibliometric), this research investigated the intellectual structure, development trend, and thematic size of ML & DL-based studies for aviation from 2015 to 2025. A total of 1,372 publications were extracted from the Web of Science database and analyzed by CiteSpace to evaluate growth in this field in general, and its interdisciplinarity in particular.

Analysis of citation clustering suggested that research consists of 16 meaningful clusters, each with a technical and application focus. The number of clusters is larger than two: Commercial Aviation and Flight Delay Prediction, indicating that, in contrast to previous years, maturity is being reached in the faltering data-driven decision support systems in aviation, flight delay prediction, and operational efficiency. Additionally, the Subcluster Automatic Threat Recognition and Remaining Useful Life Prediction ensure the successful application of DL algorithms on image processing, security scans, and predictive maintenance. The network's high modularity ($Q = 0.8413$) and Silhouette ($S = 0.9546$) suggest that the literature comprises structurally distinct but thematically coherent clusters. As demonstrated by the topic category analysis, ML/DL-based aviation research is inherently multidisciplinary. Engineering, Mechanical is the core of the literature and also indicates that some studies take an engineering-based approach, while the categories of Computer Science, Information Systems, Transportation, and Science & Technology highlight how information systems are utilized in tandem with transportation technologies. In addition, the emergence of the Remote Sensing and Public, Environmental, and Occupational Health categories reaffirms the growing significance of research on environmental data, energy efficiency, and human factors in recent years. This finding demonstrates the scope of ML and DL in aviation, extending beyond engineering processes into a range of issues including environmental sustainability, and human safety. Analysis of citation explosions has also discovered turning points in the literature. It can be argued, to a face-valid extent, that Krizhevsky, Sutskever, and Hinton's (2012) paper had the greatest impact of all listed in this survey (Strength = 6.7; 2018–2022), driving the adoption of CNN architectures in aviation systems. The GAN model described by Goodfellow, Bengio, and Courville (2016) has driven the rapid rise of deep learning in predictive modeling and generation. Post-2020, papers such as Puranik et al. (2020) and Basora et al. (2019) demonstrated a variety of ML approaches applied to predictive maintenance and flight safety.

Overall, the 2015–2025 time frame is subject to a three-stage evolutionary path: The methodological period (2015–2018)— Influenced by this incumbent research in basic deep learning architectures such as CNN, ResNet and GAN; The practical stage (between 2018–2022), focused on aviation-specific fault detection, flight delay prediction and predictive maintenance; and finally, the maturity phase between 2022 and 2025 concentrating on sustainability and energy efficiency along with environmental issues.

The implications of these findings are that, in aviation, ML and DL applications not only pertain to technical systems, but also influence decision-making processes within organizations when combined with management information systems. From the MIS perspective, the DMA processes demonstrate that ML/DL technologies support strategic planning and operational performance enhancement. For a more comprehensive paradigm, future research should focus on AI applications in aviation from the viewpoints of MIS integration, a firm's data governance, and digital transformation.

The findings confirm that ML and DL studies in aviation no longer deal solely with technological advances, but are developing into a multidisciplinary field serving environmental and operational sustainability. The work contributes to a better understanding of the intellectual structure shaping this field, catching its pioneering themes and turning points, and presenting it as an orientation framework for further investigation.

5.1. Limitations

While this study provides valuable insights into the intellectual structure and evolution of ML/DL research in aviation, four main limitations should be acknowledged that may inform future research directions.

Database Coverage: This analysis is limited to publications indexed in the Web of Science Core Collection. Although WoS is one of the most prestigious and comprehensive academic databases, it does not capture all relevant research, particularly publications in specialized conference proceedings, and regional journals outside the WoS index. Future studies could expand coverage by integrating multiple databases to provide a more comprehensive view of the field.

Keyword Dependence: The search strategy relies on explicit mentions of "machine learning," "deep learning," and "aviation" in titles, abstracts, or keywords. This approach may exclude studies that employ ML/DL techniques without these explicit terms, or that use alternative terminology such as "neural networks," "predictive analytics," or "artificial intelligence." Alternative search strategies that combine subject classification codes with broader keyword sets could mitigate this limitation.

Language Restriction: Limiting publications to English-language sources may introduce geographic and cultural bias, potentially underrepresenting important research contributions from non-English-speaking regions, particularly in aviation powerhouses such as China, Russia, and European countries with strong aviation industries. Multilingual bibliometric studies could address this gap.

Methodological Granularity: While this study identifies ML/DL methods used in leading publications, a more granular analysis of algorithm performance comparisons, dataset characteristics, and implementation challenges would provide deeper practical insights for aviation practitioners and MIS managers.

5.2. Future Research Directions

Future research should:

1. Conduct multi-database bibliometric analyses combined with industry reports and patent data to more fully capture the ecosystem of ML/DL innovation in aviation;
2. Perform qualitative content analysis to more thoroughly examine methodological choices, dataset characteristics, and implementation barriers;
3. Investigate the relationship between ML/DL research themes and aviation management practices, particularly in MIS integration, data governance, and organizational adoption;
4. Explore ethical, regulatory, and certification challenges specific to deploying ML/DL systems in safety-critical aviation contexts;
5. Examine regional variations in ML/DL aviation research to identify geographic knowledge gaps and opportunities for international collaboration.

Author Statement

Concept and design were contributed to equally by all authors. Burak Evrentuğ conducted bibliometric analyses, and the methodological design was structured. Çiğdem Bilal provided background, interpretation, and discussion of findings. The final version of the article has been read and approved by both authors.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors have no conflict of interest related to the publication of this article.

Ethical approval

This research does not involve human participants or animal experiments, and only bibliometric data from the Web of Science database is analyzed. This paper was presented at the International Conference on Aviation Management on October 23-26, 2025.

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